

Catability as a Metric for Evaluating Superposed Coherent States

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(Received 3 July 2025; revised 15 October 2025; accepted 26 January 2026; published 5 March 2026)

Superposed coherent states are central to quantum technologies, yet their reliable identification remains a challenge, especially in noisy or resource-constrained settings. We introduce a novel, directly measurable criterion for detecting catlike features in quantum states. The criterion is based on the concept of nonlinear squeezing and bypasses the need for full state tomography of the tested states. The numerical results confirm its robustness under loss and its potential for experimental implementation. The method naturally generalizes to more exotic superpositions, including multiheaded cat states.

DOI: [10.1103/physrevlett.136.090205](https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevlett.136.090205)

Superposed coherent states, also known as coherent cat states, are inspired by the famous Schrödinger thought experiment [1]. Apart from being particularly useful for discussing the foundations of quantum mechanics, they play a crucial role in practical applications; coherent cat states can be used to encode information in quantum computation [2–11], as highly sensitive probes in quantum metrology [12,13], and as fundamental resources in breeding protocols for the experimental preparation of more complex quantum states [8,14–16]. Due to their versatility, cat states are the sought-after target of many experiments; to this day, cat states of various quality have been prepared in traveling light [17–20], microwave resonators [21–23], trapped ions [24,25], atoms [26], or hybrid systems [27], and there are several proposals for their preparation in optomechanical systems [28,29].

One of the central challenges in all related experiments is the characterization of the prepared quantum states. A commonly considered indicator is non-Gaussianity of the state [30–32], commonly defined as deviation from a Gaussian shape of its Wigner function. Although there are several methods for its detection [32–36], they offer only a limited view of the nature of the state. The conventional approach used in practice utilizes fidelity [15,23,37], defined as the geometric overlap between two quantum states, to provide a more complete, global comparison of the experimentally produced state and its theoretical counterpart. Fidelity is appealing due to its intuitive interpretation, but it lacks nuance when applied to states occupying infinite-dimensional Hilbert spaces. Its

value can be affected in fundamentally different ways that are difficult to distinguish from fidelity alone. For example, low fidelity might indicate that the tested state is qualitatively different; equally it might also be a mixture of qualitatively similar states. Furthermore, fidelity typically requires full knowledge of the quantum state, which must be obtained through quantum state reconstruction [18–25,38].

A directly measurable alternative to fidelity is available in some quantum states that manifest reduced fluctuations of some observable operator. The original squeezed states [39–41] displayed reduced fluctuations in the canonical quadrature operators of harmonic oscillators. These states became indispensable for the preparation and manipulation of quantum states [18–20,42–44], with applications in quantum metrology [45] and quantum communication protocols [46,47]. When it comes to state characterization, the concept of squeezing is beneficial because it requires only a single measurement basis. While this omits some information about the state, it is often sufficient as the performance of many applications depends only on the squeezed variance of the quadrature operators [45,48–50].

The concept of squeezing can be broadened to nonlinear squeezing, where an arbitrary observable operator exhibits reduced fluctuations [51,52]. Whereas traditional squeezing principally represents a similarity to some eigenstate of a canonical quadrature operator, nonlinear squeezing characterizes correspondence to some eigenstate of the general observable. In principle, nonlinear squeezing can quantify closeness to any quantum state, which can be identified as an eigenstate of some observable. This extension can be advantageously used to evaluate the quality of complex non-Gaussian quantum states used as resources in quantum technologies, for example, those displaying cubic or quartic nonlinearity [53–56], or the Gottesman-Kitaev-Preskill states [57].

In this Letter, we identify such an operator for superposed coherent states and use it to define catability: a directly measurable quantity that can be used to identify

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and evaluate cat states, clearly showing their non-Gaussian nature. We compare its sensitivity to non-Gaussian features for decohered cat states with fidelity. We then show that its evaluation requires only three sets of number operator measurements instead of full quantum tomography. We further demonstrate that it can be generalized to a broader class of cat states.

The balanced coherent cat states are defined as

$$|\alpha, \pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{(|\alpha\rangle \pm |-\alpha\rangle)}{\sqrt{1 \pm \exp(-2|\alpha|^2)}} \quad (1)$$

and represent the ground eigenstates of a class of directly observable positive semidefinite operators

$$\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma) = (\hat{a}^{\dagger 2} - \alpha^{*2})(\hat{a}^2 - \alpha^2) + \gamma(1 \mp \hat{\Pi}). \quad (2)$$

The symbols \hat{a} and \hat{a}^\dagger are the annihilation and creation operators of the harmonic oscillator, and $\hat{\Pi}$ embodies the parity operator. The first term tests the separation of the coherent peaks, while the second term uses the parity operator to verify the presence of quantum coherence. The real parameter $\gamma > 0$ controls the importance of achieving either of these features. Regardless of its value, the ideal cat states (1) are the eigenstates of the positive semidefinite operators (2) corresponding to the lowest eigenvalue $\lambda_0 = 0$. The parameter $\gamma > 0$ in (2) represents a tunable trade-off between the two ingredients of the witness: the peak separation and the parity terms. In practice, γ balances sensitivity to branch separation versus quantum coherence. Ideal cat states remain ground states of $\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)$ for any $\gamma > 0$, and the definition of catability (3) minimizes over γ so that the optimal weight is chosen to suit the data. For very large γ , the criterion becomes primarily sensitive to parity, while for small γ it favors peak separation. In experiments, moderate γ values naturally balance both features. In our subsequent numerical analysis, we restrict $\gamma \in [0, 5]$ for convenience. In principle, the optimization is not limited to this range.

These operators can be used to define the catability of an arbitrary quantum state $\hat{\rho}$ as

$$\xi_{(\pm)}(\alpha) = \min_{\gamma} \frac{\text{Tr}(\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)\hat{\rho})}{\min_{\hat{\rho}_G} \text{Tr}(\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)\hat{\rho}_G)}, \quad (3)$$

where the minimization in the denominator is performed over the set of all Gaussian states [58]. Note that the optimization over Gaussian states needs to be performed only once. The normalization can be quickly determined using a precomputed lookup table [59]. The whole expression is minimized over all the possible $\gamma > 0$ parameters. The numerator can be interpreted as nonlinear squeezing on its own; it is the second moment of the operator

$$\sqrt{\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)} \quad (4)$$

and even becomes equal to its variance when the first moment is set to zero, similarly to the approach presented in [57]. The nonlinear squeezing can be normalized with the best value attainable by Gaussian states, making the following practical interpretation possible: (1) If $\xi_{(\pm)}(\alpha) = 0$, then $\hat{\rho}$ is an eigenstate of the operator $\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)$ and represents a perfect cat state $|\alpha, \pm\rangle$, which is necessarily non-Gaussian. (2) If $0 < \xi_{(\pm)}(\alpha) < 1$, then $\hat{\rho}$ is an imperfect, approximate cat state with amplitude α , but we can still confirm its non-Gaussian nature. (3) If $\xi_{(\pm)}(\alpha) \geq 1$, we cannot say. It might be the correct cat state with too much decoherence, a different cat state, or a different state altogether.

Imperfect or approximate cat states are understood here as realistic quantum states that may be expressed as superpositions or mixtures of ideal cat states and other components, arising, for example, from loss, decoherence, and other experimental imperfections [58].

Catability allows us to determine the quality of an experimental cat state with specific parity and amplitude α . It can also serve as a straightforward witness indicating whether an unknown state approaches the desired cat state. We can also define a global catability

$$\xi = \min_{\alpha, \pm} \xi_{(\pm)}(\alpha) \quad (5)$$

to check whether a given unknown test state is a non-Gaussian approximation of some undetermined cat state.

Let us now demonstrate the application of catability in some realistic scenarios. We consider ideal cat states (1) decohered by pure loss; this is a common occurrence in optical experiments and quickly reduces the quantum non-Gaussian properties of the affected states [60,61]. Pure loss can be modeled with an unbalanced beam splitter where the transmitted signal interacts with the environment in a vacuum state. Its amplitude transmissivity $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ determines the amount of incurred loss. The output state can be computed with Kraus operators [62]

$$\hat{\rho}_{\text{out}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \hat{M}_n \hat{\rho} \hat{M}_n^\dagger$$

$$\text{where } \hat{M}_k = \sqrt{\frac{(1-\eta^2)^k}{k!}} \eta^{\hat{a}^\dagger} \hat{a}^k. \quad (6)$$

Losing half of the signal is sufficient to remove all negativity from the Wigner functions of any non-Gaussian state [63].

We also consider approximate cat states that can be prepared from finite superpositions of photons using Gaussian squeezing $\hat{S}(r) = \exp[(r/2)(\hat{a}^2 - \hat{a}^{\dagger 2})]$. The states

$$\hat{S}(r)|1\rangle \quad \text{and} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{S}(r)(\sqrt{\omega}|0\rangle + \sqrt{1-\omega}|2\rangle) \quad (8)$$

approximate small cats with even and odd parities, respectively. These approximations are also highly susceptible to loss and appear in experiments with traveling light, where the cat states are usually generated using generalizations of photon subtraction and photon number counting techniques [18–20,60,64,65].

We evaluate the catability for these states and compare it with the well-established fidelity. To facilitate direct comparison, we introduce the normalized infidelity of a quantum state $\hat{\rho}$ with the target cat state (1) as

$$\zeta_{(\pm)}(\alpha) = \frac{1 - \langle \alpha, \pm | \hat{\rho} | \alpha, \pm \rangle}{\min_{\hat{\rho}_G} [1 - \langle \alpha, \pm | \hat{\rho}_G | \alpha, \pm \rangle]}. \quad (9)$$

To provide the same information as catability, it is normalized with the least infidelity attainable by Gaussian states. The normalized infidelity ranges from 0 for ideal cats to 1 for states with the same fidelity reachable by Gaussian approximations. It can, therefore, also serve as a witness of non-Gaussian behavior. Similarly to catability, we can construct a global normalized infidelity as

$$\zeta = \min_{\alpha, \pm} \zeta_{(\pm)}(\alpha). \quad (10)$$

We numerically evaluated the global catability and normalized infidelity for several cat states and their approximations subjected to loss. In particular, we considered even- and odd-parity cat states (1) with amplitudes $\alpha \in \{0.5, 1.5, 2.5\}$. We also analyzed their photonic approximations (7) and (8), with the tunable parameters set to $r \approx -5$ dB and $\omega = 0.618$. These values minimize the expectation value of (2) for $\alpha = 1$ and can therefore be considered optimal approximation of small cat states.

The results of the numerical simulations are presented in Fig. 1. The results for odd-parity states are organized in the left column, whereas the right column represents even states. A key observation is that even at loss levels where the normalized infidelity exceeds $\zeta > 1$, rendering the value inconclusive, catability successfully identifies cat states. Its sensitivity is strongest for small coherent states with amplitudes 0.5 and 1 and the small amplitude approximations (7) and (8). We can also see that odd cat states retain their non-Gaussianity for a greater loss; the Wigner function of even-parity cats is positive at the origin and, for small amplitudes quickly, decoheres into a form that is difficult to distinguish from a Gaussian squeezed state. Note that there is a fundamental difference in evaluation between even and odd cat states. Since the catability is normalized against Gaussian states that always have positive parity, large γ in the optimization (3) can attribute significant non-Gaussian features even to states

dissimilar from cat states. These states are still highly non-Gaussian, and the catability correctly picks up on this property. A possible way to compensate for this behavior is to choose a different class of states for normalization, such

FIG. 1. Comparison of cat states subjected to different degrees of pure loss. The red curves represent the optimal values of the normalized infidelity (9), while the blue curves correspond to the optimal values of catability (3), all relative to the transmissivity η of the loss channel. The left column shows results for odd-parity cat states and their approximations, with (a) squeezed single photon ($r \approx -5$ dB), and cats with amplitudes $\alpha^- \in \{0.5, 1.5, 2.5\}$ in panels (b)–(d), respectively. The results for even-parity states are presented in the right column, with (e) squeezed superposition of $|0\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$ ($\omega = 0.618$, $r \approx -5$ dB), and cats with amplitudes $\alpha^+ \in \{0.5, 1.5, 2.5\}$ within panels (f)–(h).

as photon-subtracted squeezed states (see Ref. [58] for details about optimization of α and γ for odd cats). In the limit of low loss, catability aligns with fidelity for larger cat states and can be seen as a way to measure fidelity with lower resources.

The most significant advantage of catability lies in the direct measurability of the operator (2), which can be decomposed into terms comprising number operators $\hat{n} = \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}$ transformed by Gaussian displacement operations $\hat{D}(\beta) = \exp[\beta^* \hat{a} - \beta \hat{a}^\dagger]$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma) &= 2\hat{n}^2 + |\alpha|^2(4\hat{n} + 1) + 2|\alpha|^4 - \hat{n} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}[\hat{D}^\dagger(\alpha)\hat{n}^2\hat{D}(\alpha) + \hat{D}(\alpha)\hat{n}^2\hat{D}^\dagger(\alpha)] \\ &\quad + \gamma(1 \mp \hat{\Pi}). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The measurement statistics of the three constituent operators, \hat{n} , $\hat{D}^\dagger(\alpha)\hat{n}^2\hat{D}(\alpha)$, and $\hat{D}^\dagger(-\alpha)\hat{n}^2\hat{D}(-\alpha)$, are functions of the probabilities $p_n(\beta) = \text{Tr}[\hat{D}^\dagger(\beta)|n\rangle\langle n|\hat{D}(\beta)\hat{\rho}]$ for any state $\hat{\rho}$ and can be used to determine the mean value of the operator (11) as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma) \rangle &= \sum_n p_n(0)[2n^2 - (1 + 4|\alpha|^2)n] \\ &\quad \mp \sum_n p_n(0)[\gamma(-1)^n] \\ &\quad + \sum_n p_n(\alpha)n^2 + \sum_n p_n(-\alpha)n^2 \\ &\quad + 2|\alpha|^4 + |\alpha|^2 \mp \gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

A benefit of this decomposition is that the measurement of the number operator is a feasible operation in all the contemporary platforms where the cat states are prepared [20,23,25]. Therefore, the three sets of measurements are sufficient to verify the existence of the cat state.

To validate the feasibility of the direct measurement, we conducted a numerical simulation designed to closely resemble an actual experiment [58]. The simulation focuses on an odd-parity cat state with initial amplitude $\alpha = 2$ subjected to different amounts of amplitude loss, specifically to 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30%.

As shown in Fig. 2(a), the results indicate that the uncertainty consistently decreases as the number of measurements increases. The standard deviation is explicitly shown in Fig. 2(b). It is the largest for the state with zero loss, a consequence of the largest effective amplitude of the initial cat state.

As a final remark, note that while the measurement of catability for a fixed α requires only three sets of measurements of displaced number operators, which is not as difficult as the full tomography typically needed for fidelity [18–20]. The global catability demands scanning over all possible values of α . When its value is known or can be coarsely estimated, for example, from the mean value of the

FIG. 2. Simulated direct measurement of the operator (12) for an odd-parity cat state with amplitude $\alpha = 2$ subjected to different levels of amplitude loss. Colors indicate 0% (red), 10% (green), 20% (blue), and 30% (yellow) loss. (a) The dashed line indicates the mean value of the operator with respect to the number of performed measurements. The shaded regions represent uncertainty up to one standard deviation. (b) The standard deviation depends on the number of measurements.

number operator [66,67], our criterion offers a practical advantage over fidelity.

On a final note, let us discuss possible generalizations. Every balanced superposition of any two coherent states can be transformed into the form (1) by a displacement operation. Superpositions of displaced squeezed states can be accommodated by squeezing the operator (2) and instead employing

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma, r) &= \hat{S}^\dagger(r)\hat{O}_{(\pm)}(\alpha, \gamma)\hat{S}(r) \\ &= ((\mu\hat{a}^\dagger - \nu\hat{a})^2 - \alpha^{*2})((\mu\hat{a} - \nu\hat{a}^\dagger)^2 - \alpha^2) \\ &\quad + \gamma(1 \mp \hat{\Pi}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mu = \cosh(r)$ and $\nu = \sinh(r)$.

Another possible generalization employs superpositions of more coherent states, resulting in the multiheaded cat states

$$|\alpha, N, m\rangle \propto \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} e^{ikm\frac{2\pi}{N}} |\alpha e^{\frac{ik2\pi}{N}}\rangle, \quad (13)$$

where N indicates the number of its heads. These states are the ground eigenstates of the adapted operator

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{O}^{(N)}(\alpha, \gamma, m) &= (\hat{a}^{\dagger N} - \alpha^{*N})(\hat{a}^N - \alpha^N) \\ &\quad + \gamma \left(1 - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} |Nk - m\rangle\langle Nk - m| \right), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $m = 1, 2, \dots, N$ characterizes the particular phase factors between the constituent coherent states. Applications of these generalizations follow straightforwardly from the discussion of the two-headed cat scenario. In the Supplemental Material [58], we demonstrate evaluation of catability for the three-headed cat state across all symmetries and compare the results with the corresponding normalized infidelity.

In conclusion, we have introduced a new framework for identifying and characterizing cat states using an indicator based on the nonlinear squeezing of an operator whose ground states are ideal cat states. This method provides a reliable and experimentally accessible alternative to fidelity, which is often limited by its interpretability and dependence on full-state reconstruction. If needed, the nonlinear operator of catability can also be used to find optimal approximations of cat states constructed from states with limited stellar rank [68–70].

Our results show that catability remains robust despite loss, efficiently distinguishing between ideal, approximate, and loss-affected cat states. It also offers the advantage of direct measurability through particle number distributions and displaced quadrature moments, enabling practical implementation in experimental setups.

Moreover, we have generalized the operator to support N -headed cat states, underlining the flexibility of the approach. As a criterion based on nonlinear squeezing, catability contributes a powerful tool for analysis of non-Gaussian quantum resources and opens new possibilities for state certification in realistic experiments [17–29,71].

Acknowledgments—We acknowledge the support of the Czech Science Foundation (Project No. 25-17472S), and European Union’s HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under Grant Agreement No. 101080173 (CLUSTEC). J. P. further acknowledges Europe Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreements No. 101017733 and No. 731473 (CLUSSTAR). P. M. acknowledges the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic Reg. No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004649. V. K. acknowledges IGA_PrF_2025_010. We also thank Michal Matulík and Jaromír Fiurášek for the valuable discussions. We acknowledge use of the computational cluster at the Department of Optics at Palacký University and use of several open-source software libraries [72–74] in the computation, evaluation, and presentation of the results.

Data availability—The datasets supporting the presented results, along with the source code used for their creation, are publicly available [59].

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